

Symbiotic Cohabitation

A typological approach in restructuring the fringe of village Burail

Thesis Report - Mayank Ojha

Certificate

I hereby recommend the thesis report titled "Symbiotic Cohabitation - A typological approach in restructuring the fringe of Burail " prepared by Mayank Ojha, under my guidance, be accepted as a requirement for partial fulfilment of the degree of Bachelors of Architecture.

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Prelude

Chandigarh has been widely discussed since its initial conception, planning and design by Le Corbusier and his team, often criticized under both positive and negative light. However, the peculiarities arising from this intervention and its implications go unnoticed and unrealised, as evident from the current practices in both urban design and architecture in one of the fastest growing economies of the world.

The 1999 convention celebrating the golden jubilee of the city stood apart and focussed on issues regarding the peripheral slum developments, village outgrowths and the satellite towns. However, it did not lay any emphasis on the city's inner boundaries that cast islands of urbanized villages which are rapidly deteriorating to become its backyards. The once prospering agrarian villages are inheriting slum like characteristics and socio-economic backwardness.

Thus the larger intent of this thesis is to familiarise oneself with the relation of the village to its forced inclusion into the urban framework; thereby, initiating a search seeking possibilities/proposals for a 'symbiotic cohabitation' of such villages and the city as a whole, without outrightly rejecting either of the two polar forms of architecture/urbanism. The focus is on understanding the conditions emanating at the interface of the universally accepted modernist planning and the omnipresent, traditionally developed agrarian villages.

The design approach is inspired by the recent developments in the interpretations of the type and typologies as recognized in the Jan-Feb issue of AD pursued by students at the Diploma 6 unit of AA, London under the guidance of Christopher Lee & Sam Jacoby and the familiarisation, exposure & experience gained during my internship at SERIE architects, Mumbai. Thus, I have tried to explore the ongoing academic and practical architectural scenarios of urban villages in backdrop of Chandigarh. Typological working has been brought to use to fulfil the hollowness of the widespread developments responding to rapid urbanization, changing needs & challenges and a market economy, driven by the need to innovate just for the sake of it.

REPORT STRUCTURE

This report is structured into three sections. The first one introduces the urban villages, their place relative to the assumed poles of urbanization - cities & villages, characteristics owed to their inception, evolution and the relations with the city. Here, the unique status of the villages in Chandigarh's context is also discussed. The second section aims at a detailed analysis of the village Burail, and its socio-economic aspects. The third section includes articles related to type and typological working, case studies which help in understanding types in the local context and the methodology and approach to achieve the objectives for the design of an architectural intervention exploiting the potentials of interface between the urbanized villages and the city.

Synopsis

Introduction

The brief for the design part of the thesis is constructed overlooking the feasibility of the available land, acquisitions, mortgages, compensations etc. and is taken up as a hypothetical project starting with the following assumptions.

The Chandigarh Administration wants to include the development of urbanized villages in its future planning and through a pilot project, a physical intervention is proposed into the extended abadi area to seek an addition of a new layer to the city's evolutionary process. The village Burail is thus chosen considering various factors. Henceforth, the thesis seeks the answers to the following questions that shall guide the research preceding the design of such an intervention:

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- What part of the village should be taken up, which shall reciprocate a maximum impact of the intervention, in a productive sense?
- What shall be the program for such an intervention?
- What can be inherited from the modernist planning principles and the traditional growth?
- How would the architectural character associate with the opposing contexts on either side?
- What other potentials does this unique urban condition exhibit?
- How can a new architectural 'type' originate from it?

These questions help in framing the following objectives for the research which shall further aid the diagram for the designing and organization of the spatial and physical environment.

Objectives

- Interpreting the traditional architecture, especially the spatial types, of a village into urban context.
- The design shall seek to identify the forces that would shape a contemporary architecture in response to a changing society and unique urban conditions.
- To identify generators for the design diagram as inherited from both the design process of the city as well as the historicity (the quality of being part of recorded history) of the village.
- The advanced objective shall seek the possibility of coexistence of the network of existing villages within the urban framework. Thus, benefitting the various communities associated

Validity

with them and helping in the inclusive growth of the city.

The knowledge gained shall be of importance in understanding the relations between a mature, urbanized village and the city in which it is engulfed. It will help in the planning and thus a better integration of villages soon to be engulfed within the urban framework, in a mutually beneficial way for both entities as well as the various associated communities.

The hypothesis for the research looks into the following benefits to be availed by the citizens:

- Easy availability of goods and services at reduced prices, owing to low rentals, negligible transportation costs, compressed supply chain and a minimized catchment area.
- This implies a reduced footprint of the city.
- Alternate sources of income and economic opportunities for the native villager population and the migrant workforce, without having to commute across the city.
- The survival and sustenance of small-scale cottage industries with an increased demand and a far-reaching market.
- Reduced burden on the administration to provide for housing, infrastructure, amenities and employment to the migrant workforce that is assimilated within the developing interface and reduces the development of peripheral slums.

Thus, the approach aims at an inclusive development of the city from hereon, not ignoring the existing or the unplanned parts, or the specific communities that were not included in the initial conception of the city.

Scope & Limitations

The thesis project is divided into two parts, the research part and the design part. The objective is that all questions arising from a critique of the design should have answers in the research carried out during the initial stages.

The scope of the thesis project includes the development of a commercial complex through a proto-typical design process, as would be deduced from the research. The fusion of economic activities with spaces for leisure/ recreation as well as facilitating the lower strata of the society

- migrant hawkers, vendors & daily wage earners.

However, neither the research nor the approach targets the interior of the village or the residential segments. These parts of the village, although exhibit a large scope for improvement and potential for a 'symbiotic co-existence' with the city, would require a dedicated research project, which lies beyond the scope of a B-Arch Xth sem thesis project.

Here, the area of focus shall be restricted to the commercial belt at the interface of the village and the city.

Therefore, the methodology in conducting the research and the subsequent design follows the following sequence:

1. Framing research questions - objectives, that would help in satisfying the brief.
2. Understanding the Urban Villages in general and seeking similarities between socio-economic and physical aspects arising from the process of urbanization and forced inclusion.
3. Understanding the Urban Villages in the context of Chandigarh, their unique aspects and characteristics.
4. Selection of an appropriate site in the urban village based on parameters such as - degree of urbanization/maturity of urban village, availability of a maximum number of forces/factors such as existing activities, challenges etc.
5. Researching these factors in details and deducing inferences regarding their relation with the physical/spatial environment.
6. Researching the patterns and principles behind organization and functioning of various activities that exist at the site, as well as shortlisting those which would help in attaining the objectives.
7. Generating a diagram for the design with the intention of bridging the contrasting characters of the city and the village while at the same time transgressing the existing building/container types to produce a new architecture responding to the socio-economic parameters and the unique urban condition.
8. Design detailing based on the diagram.

Methodology

Chapter 1

Urban Village

Urban Village

DEFINATION

Urban village is a post-modern condition, wherein a formerly agrarian village which gets engulfed by a city in its proximity which grows to the point of altering its social fabric and economic patterns. It is a global phenomenon, although largely witnessed in developing nations and can be read as an outcome of rapid urbanization which results from migration of rural population from surrounding regions who are seeking to be a part of the growing city. It partially retains its village identity in terms of social ties and physical environment whereas its urbanisation changes its means of sustenance.

The meaning of an urban village varies in reference to the context and the part of the world in question. A generalized definition for an Urban Village may not be feasible, but certain common characteristics can be deduced from the typical evolutionary process which govern the face of the urban village within the city. Various examples highlight the universal presence of urban villages in a variety of urban conditions. The degree of political influence and economic pressure of surrounding city result in different appearances of the urban villages.

The 'Urban Village' terminology marketed in the western world by real estate developers and some academia, which inherits values from traditional settlements and tries to emulate a socio-physical environment in sub-urban communities. This is part of the New Urbanism movement, and differs from the urban village being referred to here.

Opposite - Aerial view of an Urban Village set within recent planned development

INCEPTION

Most of the villages developed as agglomerations of agricultural communities serving an agricultural zone around them, they dot these expanses of land in between the different cities and bear varied influence of urbanisation on them. The villages which are located just beyond the outer periphery of cities develop into urban villages due to extension of selective urban facilities and propagation of non-agrarian trade into the core of villages.

As the cities expand, some peripheral village lands (farmlands, common lands as well as private land) are acquired and rehabilitated, while others successfully resist

being bought over. Although farm land gets acquired but the area within lal dora is retained.

The latter, once engulfed by the expanding cities, are deemed as 'villages in city' by marking an inner limit for the city's expansion (this inner limit coincides with the habitation limit of the village), and a boundary to protect the village island. This initiates the urbanization process of the 'protected' village, which mature into Urban Villages in consideration.

Conversely urban villages have originated in several parts of china as a result of its special economic zone policy. Under this policy Chinese government planted various worker villages to establish new towns. Once the towns were ready for discharge, the villages were seen as mere blots of unwanted pastures in the ready to progress cities. These villages urbanised to certain extend under the influence of peripheral towns. However, at the core it retains its village characteristics.

EVOLUTION

As identified earlier, the urban villages share a broadly similar urbanisation process distributed over similar progression stages as discussed below:

- Soon after earmarking the boundary of the "protected" village and with the city around it growing, the village becomes a counter magnet to the city for a workforce constituting migrants and labourers as it offers reasonable infrastructure, daily necessities and suitable living conditions.
- The villagers (the original farmers) seize the economic opportunity, and with their primary occupation non-existent, turn into land-owners, landlords and entrepreneurs by constructing tenements for the floating workforce within the village fabric.
- Commercial, economic activities within the village witness a boom and attract people to open shops for retail and services for the village population.
- This embarks a sociological and economical transformation process and the entire structuring of the village is shaken as it swells to its limits accompanied by vertical growth, embedding streets and leftover spaces.
- The boundary, edge or more precisely, the 'Fringe', becomes the most active zone within the 'protected' village

area by acting as an interface between the village and the city.

UNIVERSALITY

The universality of the phenomena is justified by the omnipresence of such co-habiting settlements throughout the world. A few of them are listed below:

China's Urbanization plan - '400 cities before 2020' creates a soviet-style infrastructure grid for an SEZ city around existing rural villages, creating 'Village in Cities'.
(source: Research Paper, Yushi Uehara)

Urban Kampung, Indonesia - as many as 20-25% of the total population of Jakarta lives in such 490 pockets which are not even administrative entities.
(source: research paper; www.unhabitat.org)

Delhi state's 5 community development blocks comprise of 209 villages in all, of which 10 are uninhabited while 135 are notified as 'urbanized'.
(source: www.delhigovt.nic.in; notified between 1966-2002)
Many of Mumbai's original fishing villages have already succumbed to economic and political pressures and degraded as slums in the infills of the urban fabric.

Chandigarh Context

Legal framework - Agrarian villages

The villages in this region, prior to the establishment of the city of Chandigarh, formed a constellation of agrarian villages between expanses of agricultural land. In order to restrict the expansion of the settlements displacing agricultural lands, the prevalent norms since imperial times, defined a *lal dora* (literally a Red Line) as the boundary of the village. This usually coincided with a *phirni* (a circulatory road).

Within the *lal dora*, the land was earmarked as either *abadi deh*, i.e. privately owned parcels of land where residential/commercial establishments can be constructed, or as *shamilat deh*, which was collectively owned land for community activities. This maintained a balance of open/contained as well as private/community spaces.

Urban Villages in Chandigarh

DEVELOPMENT OF THE CITY

The following text traces the inception of the urbanization process of the villages in the region:

- The city of Chandigarh, as planned by Le Corbusier and his associates, had the Dakshin Marg as its southern limit for the First Phase. During this phase, all villages located in the sector areas were acquired and the population rehabilitated.
- After the trifurcation of Punjab in 1966, Chandigarh became a Union Territory and joint capital of 2 states. Many state and central government offices were shifted or set up in the city, thus demanding the expansion of the city.
- The Second Phase was planned for the city, comprising of the sector no.'s 26-47. It was in this phase that the existing villages of Burail, Buterla, Badheri, Attawa restricted acquisitions and continue to coexist within the city's fabric.

The Municipal Corporation, Chandigarh which came into existence later in the year 1995, got transferred the villages falling in the grid namely Attawa, Buterla, Badheri and Burail. The maintenance and development control of these villages was thereafter a responsibility of the Municipal Corporation, Chandigarh. However, due to a lack of building bye laws for the development control of these villages, they continued to grow in a haphazard manner resulting in conflicting land use and defective circulation patterns.

GROWTH & EVOLUTION

As these villages got engulfed by the expanding city, the primary source of sustenance of the village's character and the livelihood of the communities ceased to exist. In its absence, alternative sources are sought, and this is what catapults the urbanization process and guides the growth trajectory of the villages. Along with these, other major factors that promote the growth of the villages include:

- Migration: It is the prime factor for the residential growth in the village. Migration of people seeking economic opportunities in the new city continued from rural areas across the country. Lack of residential facilities offered within the 'planned' part of the city forced the migrants to either settle in labour colonies or slums, or lease tenements in the village. The latter, though limited in number, is the preferred choice owing to established infrastructure, availability of daily necessities and reasonable living

Chandigarh region, showing the proliferation of Urban Villages (Red) across the city and neighbouring towns of Panchkula and Mohali. The highlighted area (Grey) shows Phase II sectors

conditions.

- Policies: as the 'planned city' grew, the demand for products and services multiplied. The stringent bye-laws and controls for various zoned areas exclude certain activities which take refuge in the village. Thus the villages become repositories - islands of relaxed control within the city.
- Economics: along with flexibility of space, program and growth, the relative cheapness of land within the village limits, the native habitants, seeking alternative sources of livelihood, exploit the conditions, especially at the 'Fringes' of the village by leasing out spaces for economic activities including retail, services, small-scale/cottage industries, dairy farming etc.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE INTERFACE

Traditionally, architecture was regarded as the tangible reflection of a society. This was so where the physical environment evolved according to the changes, challenges and potentials arising from within the socio-economic apparatus of the settlements.

Here at Chandigarh, the resultant interface between the developing city and the existing villages owing to the pace of urbanization and freedom from bye-laws and controls, led to individuals exploiting the potential of the unique urban conditions thus emanating. Thus, the 'fringe' of the village becomes a counter magnet to the city's activities.

Challenges & Potentials

This development at the interface, has a lot of implications, both positive and negative, upon the village it contains and the city around it. However, these can be taken as the challenges and the potentials that this unique urban condition poses for future development of the planned city and the pre-existing villages, now co-existing as parts of the urban setup.

CHALLENGES

- The intensity of activity and its spillage onto circulation and access paths restricts the accessibility and hence the proliferation of commercial/economic activities to the exterior face of the interface, thereby physically cutting-off the village contained within.
- The 'fringe' also casts a division in the social fabric of the city. This is due to the following reasons: 1. the native inhabitants of the village have strong socio-cultural ties

within themselves compared to the cosmopolitan nature of the city residents 2. the physically impenetrable interface especially for the city residents limits interaction amongst the communities 3. the physical boundary of the village coincides with the economic boundaries, i.e. the average incomes of people inhabiting the village are relatively lower than those living adjacent but across the fringe in the planned part of the city

- Owing to the rapid growth of the fringe area, the development is haphazard, lacking spacial quality and inefficient circulation patterns.
- In the absence of land management mechanisms existing in the village interior or the stringent zoning of the city, any remaining open spaces succumb to commercial pressures and are either used for storage, spillage of activities or are encroached by hawkers and vendors.
- The fringe area neither inherits the traditional qualities of the village in terms of planning, architectural/spatial character, nor the organized and ordered character of the modernist city. Most of the buildings have an incoherent, ad-hoc outlook aimed to achieve economic efficiency or stand out amongst its neighbours.

POTENTIALS

However, the unique urban conditions that arise from the inclusion of the village within the city and the subsequent development of the interface posits the following potentials:

- Easy availability of goods, services at reduced prices, owing to low rentals, negligible transportation costs, compressed supply chain and a minimized catchment area.
- This implies a reduced footprint of the city.
- Alternate sources of income and economic opportunities for the native villager population and the migrant workforce, without having to commute across the city.
- The survival and sustenance of small-scale cottage industries with an increased demand and a far-reaching market.
- Reduced burden on the administration to provide for housing, infrastructure, amenities and employment to the migrant workforce that is assimilated within the developing interface and reduces the development of peripheral slums.

Guidelines for Reference

CHANDIGARH ADMINISTRATION LAND-USE PROVISIONS & CHANDIGARH INDUSTRIAL POLICY

In order to construct the brief for the proposed intervention, the following documents provide the required guidelines for design, contained program and other factors.

The permitted Land Use for the villages is governed by the Chandigarh Administration which allows the following uses:

- Residential & commercial uses
- No Industrial activity except for existing household industries as per Department of Industries, Chandigarh Administration - Chandigarh Industrial Policy, 2009
- Industries labelled as 'Green', & a few polluting industrial activities exempted from the rule like atta-chakki's, bakery products, bamboo/cane products, hosiery/apparel/garments, electronic assembly, furniture etc.
- No obnoxious trade/non-conforming uses causing nuisance/detrimental to health, environment. &/or interest of public/society shall be allowed.

These include the following limitations,

- The Chandigarh Administration may relax any of the provisions of these building rules for reasons to be recorded in writing.
- It is envisaged that most of the area will be used for pedestrian traffic. Four wheeled traffic will be allowed only on the main loop streets.

Thus, the land-use provisions allow for almost all the existing activities with the exception for the automobile service & repair shops, which is categorized with an 'Orange' label as per the Department of Industries, Chandigarh and hence cannot exist legally, or without consent.

The restriction and presumption of four wheelers to only be allowed on the loop streets, without any traffic regulations and provisions for parking, logistic services or segregation is already a grave problem and hence needs to be taken care of.

NATIONAL STREET VENDOR POLICY

Street vending as a profession has been in existence in India since times immemorial. Street Vendors provide valuable services to the urban population while trying to earn a livelihood and it is the duty of the State to protect the right of this segment of population to earn their livelihood. Thus, the National Policy aims to ensure that this important section of the urban population finds recognition for its contribution to society, and is conceived of as a major initiative for urban poverty alleviation.

Street vendor is broadly defined as a person who offers goods or services for sale to the public without having a permanent built up structure in a street.

This Policy recognises three basic categories of Street Vendors.

- Street Vendors who carry out vending on a regular basis with a specific location;
- Street Vendors who carry out vending not on a regular basis and without a specific location, for example, Vendors who sell goods in weekly bazaars during holidays and festivals and so on;
- Mobile Street Vendors.

The specific objectives of the Policy include the following:

- Legal: To give Street Vendors legal status by formulating appropriate laws and providing legitimate hawking zones in urban development/ zoning plans and ensuring their implementation;
- Facilities: To provide facilities for appropriate use of identified space including the creation of hawking zones in the urban development/ zoning plans, mentioned above;
- Regulation: To eschew imposing numerical limits on access to public spaces by discretionary licenses and instead moving to nominal fee-based regulation of access, where previous occupancy of the space by the Street Vendor for vending purposes, determines the allocation of space.
- The Municipal Authorities should regulate allocation of space based on previous occupancy. If demand for space is in excess of supply, a transparent system of selection such as lottery should be followed. All allotments should be based on payment of a prescribed fee fixed by the Municipal Authorities based on the recommendation of the

OBJECTIVES

SPATIAL PLANNING NORMS

- Town Vending Committees.
- Role in distribution: To make Street Vendors a special component of the urban development /zoning plans by treating them as an integral and legitimate part of the urban distribution system;
- Self Regulation: To promote self-regulation in matters relating to hygiene, including disposal of waste amongst Street Vendors both in the individually allotted areas as well as in areas occupied by the Street Vendors as a whole.
- Organization
- Participation
- Rehabilitation of Child Vendors
- Social Security
- Promotional Measures

Spatial Planning norms for demarcation of vending zones: The demarcation of hawking zones should be city/town specific. To make the plans conducive and adequate for the Street Vendors of the respective city / town, the following should be adhered to:

a) It should take into account the natural propensity of the Street Vendors to locate in certain places at certain times in response to patterns of demand for their goods/services. Therefore, this Policy recommends conducting surveys of Street Vendors and their location by competent professional institutions. This will be sponsored by the Ministry of Urban Employment & Poverty Alleviation/ concerned department of State Governments/ Municipal Authorities.

b) City Authorities should provide sufficient spaces, designated as 'Vendors markets' in layout plans at locations of such natural markets. The Municipal Authorities should regulate allocation of space based on previous occupancy. All allotments should be based on payment of a prescribed fee fixed by the Municipal Authorities based on the recommendation of the TVCs.

c) Mobile urban vending should be permitted in all areas even outside the designated Vendors' markets, unless designated as 'no-vending zone' through a participatory process. The 'no-vending zones' may be notified both in terms of location and

time.

d) With the growth of city/town every new area should have adequate provisions for Street Vendors.

e) Designation of Vendors markets / no-vending zones should not be left to the sole discretion of any civic or police authority, but, must be accomplished by a participatory process by TVCs, to be constituted by the Municipal Authorities. It will consist of the following:

- Designated official of Municipal Authorities;
- Traffic and Local Police;
- Public Land Owning Authority;
- Representative from associations of Street Vendors; and,
- Representative from a bank in the local area.

The Street Vendors' representatives should preferably constitute at least 25% to 40% of the total number of members of the TVCs. At least 1/3rd of the representatives of Street Vendors should be women. Process for selection of Street Vendors' representatives should be based on the following criteria:

- Membership based organisations
- Financial Accountability

f) Provisions of space may include temporary designation as Vendors' markets (e.g. as weekly markets) whose use at other times may be different (e.g. Public Park, parking lot). Timing restriction on urban vending should correspond to the needs of ensuring non-congestion of public spaces / public hygiene.

Chapter 2

Burail - Site & Context

Burail Selection Criteria

In order to fully understand and incorporate the contextual forces and socio-economic parameters, the potentials and challenges posed by an urban village, a mature stage of urbanization of the village is needed to be considered for selecting the site. However, such mature urban villages within the city do not have enough open spaces or sites that would allow a parallel intervention to happen.

At the same time, the impact of development within the city's limits, i.e. outside the village phirni would lack the impact and relation with the village and create further congestion on an already congested periphery of the villages.

Thus, these paradoxical requirements accounted for the hypothetical nature of the project. In order to explore and achieve the research objectives, the selection of an urbanized village from amongst those existing within the Chandigarh region is based on the following criteria:

- Degree of maturity (i.e. urbanization)
- Degree of interaction with the city, i.e physical integration as well as role played in the socio-economic scenario
- Partial retention of the original village fabric, social structures, architectural character, etc.
- Size - area & population

Thus, amongst the villages engulfed within the sectoral grid of the city, Burail satisfies all these objectives.

Chandigarh Phase II - 4 villages falling within the sectoral grid

Chandigarh Villages (Phase 2)
Population comparison

Area comparison (Hectares)

**FIGURE-GROUND PLAN - BURAIL &
SURROUNDING SECTORS**

A Figure-Ground plan of the village and the surrounding areas shows the contrasting models of urbanism, the traditionally evolved village as a built mass with clearings for public spaces, and the modernist conception of the city as an open plane with isolated building blocks and slabs.

Historical Outline

TIMELINE - IMPORTANT EVENTS

Burail lies nested within the sectoral framework of the city of Chandigarh, as part of Sector 45, which was developed around it during the IInd Phase of the city's development. It is an Urbanized Village with the urbanization process beginning simultaneously with the inception of the city, but the actual growth boom took place during the 1980's when the village served as a low cost dormitory between Chandigarh and the developing industrial town of Mohali.

Since, then this urbanised village has grown manifold in floating population who work as commercial helps and migrant labours in the city of Chandigarh. They get a restricted share of urban facilities courtesy its transfer to the municipal corporation in 1996. Though it doesn't enjoy complete urban facilities yet it cannot be called singled out as a village either.

EVOLUTION - THE 'FRINGE'

Burail developed in its initial phases as a typical agrarian village, although due to its topography, a raised mound in the middle allowed for the construction of a fort as a defence outpost for the mughal governor. Land around the fort was reserved (as *abadi deh*) for the residences of *zamindars* and farmers who worked on the agricultural lands extending beyond.

With the development of Chandigarh and increasing pressures of urbanization, the *lal dora* was breached with commercial and residential structures being constructed on agricultural land beyond the *phirni*. However, the pace of development grew exponentially once the master plan for the IInd Phase of Chandigarh was ready, and the plan for sector 45, exempted the constructions beyond the *lal dora*. The *phirni* for the village was revised and integrated with the circulation structure of the sector. It was during the 1980's and the 1990's that the extended *abadi* area witnessed immense construction activity

Burail (encircled) in the 1964-68 Geological Survey of India - accessed from the road connecting Chandigarh and the developing township of Mohali

and buildings containing shops, service outlets, workshops, tenements, motels/guesthouses were built, which characterise the commercial belt today. It is this zone, that forms an interface between the residential pockets of sector 45 and the village, which shall be referred to hereafter as the 'Fringe' of the village.

CURRENT STATUS

The fringe zone with its various activities exploiting the unique conditions, as discussed earlier, specializes the role of Burail as it participates in the socio-economic setup of the city. These include:

- Apart from residences of the native village population, the village also caters as a low cost dormitory for migrant labour and daily wagers, who prefer it over peripheral slums for various reasons discussed earlier. Currently, the migrants account for upto 70% of the total population of Burail.
- As a repository for commercial/economic activities that are excluded from the city, owing to stringent policies, byelaws & controls, as well as high land values, apart from the general, the village specializes in certain goods and services which can not be availed in other markets of the city or would be priced much higher.
- The village acts as a workshop for outsourced activities in order to cut down costs of space, or avail the cheap, skilled labour which dwells here itself.

Thus, the role of Burail, especially the 'Fringe' with commercial/economic activities can be judged as a service centre for the city along with catering to the local needs for not only the residents of sector 45, but adjacent sectors as well.

FUTURE TRAJECTORIES

The current population of Burail is estimated at 38,493 with the last census figures at 25,909. The growth rate of the village has been steadily maintained at greater than 35%, even though the rate of the city's growth has dropped to 17%. This throws some light on the scenario wherein the existing fabric is either being densified or the native village population is shifting to other parts of the city whereas their homes are leased out to a large number of migrants who live in cramped conditions.

'Fringe' zone - Burail, Extended abadi area (shaded)

Left - The Burail fort,
Above - A chaupal (meeting place) in one of the neighbourhoods of the village

MCC Village Byelaws

To prevent further chaos and congestion, this trend has been recognized by the administration and byelaws to control the growth of the village had been proposed, although they are currently on hold due to various shortcomings.

The following is a brief outline of those byelaws which specifically pertain to new commercial developments within the village limits, along with the observations.

- The Floor Area Ratio and the Site Coverage parameters for buildings to be constructed do not provide any incentive for the owners to redevelop the existing constructions.
- The number of permitted floors is in contradiction with the minimum specified floor-to-floor height which should be at least 9'. This would invite violations.
- Although the existing embedded streets, a 'handshake' typology, restrict proper light & ventilation to habitable spaces, the proposed model does not utilize the setback space optimally, as it would be enclosed & privatized, which is non-compliant with such a dense fabric as it cannot meet the multi-utility requirements.

Existing statistics for a typical half acre site (Kesho Ram Complex)

Max. Height - 55' (G+4)
Site Coverage - 88%
FAR - 3.0

Proposed bye-laws - for site area > half acre

Height - 58' (G+3)
Site Coverage - 30%
FAR - 1.2
Basement -
Single (upto 1 acre)
Double (> 1 acre)

The Interface

'Fringe' Taxonomy

PARAMETERS

The interface that develops primarily as a commercial zone at the fringes of the village follows certain patterns. The entire belt can be divided into various zones based on contextual parameters to analyse the factors that govern the location of various activities, the affect of the physical interaction of the village with the city's circulation pattern, i.e. The hierarchy of roads and streets as well as the emerging ownership and customer patterns.

ACTIVITIES

The parameters taken into account for the classification of the fringe zone form a nested hierarchy with reciprocal implications. However the primary parameter, common to all others is the nature of constituting activities that exist within a zone. A general list of activities existing in the fringe zone for Burail comprises of the following types:

- Retail - shops, stores etc.
- Services - exist independently or accompanied with retail or workshops
- Workshops
- Offices
- Hospitality - including budget motels/guest houses, mostly of bed & breakfast type

None of these activities exist in isolation in any part of the fringe. In all places, there is mix of activities, not only over a same street or in a single block but also in a single building. Here the understanding of the following factors which govern their location in general becomes pertinent. These can be classified based upon their source:

Dependency over customer groups

- Nature of thorough traffic
- Nature of residential population

Dependency over circulation path

- Accessibility
- Parking
- Frontage / Edge condition

Other factors

- Aggregation & Exclusion

Distribution of commercial activities within the village showing the accumulation at the outer face of the fringe zone as well as in bazaars along the old phirni.

- Mixed Use - Commercial activities primarily on ground floor
- All floors supporting commercial activities

Ownership pattern: Showing the majority trend in retailer/ service providers locations

Customer pattern: Showing the majority trend for customer groups availing the services

- Majority village residents
- Majority city residents
- Mixed / No fixed pattern

OWNERSHIP PATTERN/CUSTOMER GROUPS

The accessibility and extent of penetration into the fringe zone largely governs the nature or patterns of ownership as well as the customer base for commercial activities. At majority of the places, the fringe is impenetrable and hence most of the buildings/shops/service outlets are either owned by or leased to people hailing from the city. Whereas almost all the shops along the internal bazaars are owned by people dwelling in the village itself.

Correspondingly, the shops and services at the interface have their target customer base majorly comprising of the residents of the city whereas the internal shops cater solely to the local population.

Apart from being an important parameter for the taxonomy and assessment, this shows how the limited accessibility of the village interior and the resulting pattern limits the social interactions between the residents living on either side of the village and strengthens the divide in the social fabric.

ACCESS PATTERN / CIRCULATION TYPE

The impact of the hierarchical circulation pattern of the city's sector unit is discussed in terms of the nature of traffic, accessibility and parking. These play a major role in governing the location and operation of activities and hence, act as a parameter for the classification of the fringe belt.

1. V3 Road (Sector 45/46)

- High-speed intra-city traffic
- No direct access to establishments
- Lack of parking/lay-by space for commuters

2. V4 Road (Sector 45)

- Thorough sector traffic
- Residential population of 45-C&D served from primarily from this road
- Direct access to shops
- Availability of abundant parking and lay-by space

3. V5 Road - (Sector 45-A)

- Primary artery serving populations of more than half the village and 45-A
- Main village access branches off here
- Thoroughfare, with road opening directly into V3's
- Adjoining open spaces act as large parking lots

4. V5 Road - (Sector 45-B)

- No-thoroughfare, serves as rear-lane for institutional buildings
- Small residential population of 45-B does not commute through the entire stretch
- Ample space for parking, lay-by's

Circulation pattern - Major types of the hierarchical network of the sector intersecting with the *phirni*

The V5 road, Sector 45-A forming an interface between the village and the city

AGGREGATION

Owing to various factors, certain activities are forced out of a particular place. In the case of Burail, activities shifted from various parts of the city and sought refuge here. These included auto-repair & service centres, workshops, budget hotels etc. primarily due to the stringent policies, high costs of land and lack of flexibility and freedom to modify the physical

container according to the needs and specificities of different trades.

EXCLUSION

Here, at the fringe, other factors such as the vendors seeking a competitive environment open outlets adjacent to each other leading to such places specialising for one or the other activity. It is also promotes commercially viability as specialized hubs attracts a greater number of customers. However, aggregation only helps activities which benefit from such a competitive and specialized environment.

Impact Assessment

In order to achieve the design objectives, especially those which require the exploration and understanding of the factors, constraints and forces affecting the translation of concepts into physical form relating or associating typologically to the context, a single zone which would receive and reciprocate the maximum positive impact of the intervention needs to be taken up. Therefore, to assess the proposed impact, the following parameters have been analysed in the various zones.

PARAMETERS

The parameters include:

- Nature of residential settlement/people residing adjacent to the zone
- The nature of circulation path - hierarchical position
- Connectivity with the village

Thus, a transferable freehold ownership of houses will receive a greater impact than government allotted housing. Similarly, the middle income groups and the lower strata of the society is more likely to benefit from an intervention including various programs at the fringe than higher income groups.

The nature of circulation paths carries along with it the information regarding the type of traffic (thoroughfare, local), edge conditions (accessible or not), etc

Lastly, the connectivity with the internal pattern of the village's circulation is important to observe how the village residents perforate through a particular zone.

	The following data presents an analysis of the zones based on the above discussed parameters:		
ZONES 1	<p>Low to medium density, leasehold residences across the road, but the lack of frontage and long effective commute distance does not allow any direct interaction with the zone.</p> <p>Abutting onto V3 road, but lack of direct access and the thorough, intra-city high speed traffic restricts the commercial viability of activities.</p> <p>Limited flow of village traffic across the zone, again due to lack of direct opening from the V3 road.</p>		Impact assessment of various zones of the Fringe area
ZONES 2	<p>Medium to high density housing across the circulatory road, with the residents dependent on the zone's shops for daily needs & necessities.</p> <p>Thorough intra-sector traffic on V4 road facilitates commercial viability owing to direct parking and access to shops, stores, offices & hotels.</p> <p>Moderate access to village's interior network, primarily at the northern tip of the zone.</p>		
ZONES 3	<p>Medium to high density government housing, dependent on the zone for market necessities. Also, the most affected residences owing to high degree of congestion and chaos of traffic, thorough & parked.</p> <p>V5 street with local and thorough traffic, allowing direct access to the zone's buildings.</p> <p>Entry node serving a major part of the village, owing to the growth pattern around the original access road to the village. (as shown in map - bottom-right)</p>		
ZONES 4	<p>Small number of low density private housing, availing existing facilities from Zone 3.</p> <p>Lack of thoroughfare, allowing for a few godowns, workshops and industrial activities to exist.</p> <p>Moderate accessibility to interior network.</p>		
ZONES 5	<p>Lack of residential population, the zone faces the back of institutional buildings.</p> <p>Lack of a thorough artery, only the village circulatory road serves the zone.</p> <p>Minimal extension of the village network through the zone.</p>		

TAXONOMY - IDENTIFIED ZONES

Site Analysis

SITE SELECTION

The site for the project, as part of Zone 3, shall thus, receive and reciprocate a maximum impact of an intervention aimed at the restructuring of the fringe. The following information describes it quantitatively:

- Area : 19,465.75 sq.m. (4.81 acres)
- Permissible FSI : 1.2
- No. of floors allowed : 2 basements + G + 3
- Maximum height : 17.6m

Zone of Influence AT CITY SCALE

..... Distances to major transportation nodes

Major commercial belts / city centres

Industrial hubs

Fruit, Vegetable & Grain market

AT SECTOR SCALE

- 17th century Burail Fort
- Places of Worship - (temples, gurudwaras & mosque)
- V3 roads dividing Sector 45 with 44 & 33
- - - V5 street through Sector 45, 'A'
- Chaupals
- Site extents
- Hawkers/Street Vendors (Clusters of 1-5, 5-10, more than 10)

Climatic Information

TEMPERATURE & PRECIPITATION

Mean monthly temperature range(deg. Celsius)
(For Chandigarh)

Mean monthly precipitation totals(mm)
(For Chandigarh)

BIMONTHLY WIND EVENT TOTALS

Context

Socio-economic Aspects

The approach towards this project follows the following sequence of priorities:

People > Spaces > Buildings

Therefore, the foremost analysis comprises of the various communities that inhabit the village and those which would be affected with the intervention at the selected site.

DEMOGRAPHICS

The social fabric of the city, can be distinctly divided into the following based on the places of residence or the economic hierarchy attached with it. These are:

- The upper class residents living in houses of sizes more than 1 kanal (500 sq.yards)
- A stratified middle class living in freehold marla houses, CHB flats & apartments or government housing
- Residents of the Urban Villages
- Residents of slums at the periphery of the city.

A general reading of the data regarding the demographics of the area, the village, the surrounding sector (45) sourced from the 2001 census of India presents the following observations regarding the people, their settlement pattern, etc.

- The density of people living within the boundaries of the village is 10 times the average of phase 2 sectors.
- The social structure of the village still follows the traditional divisions according to location based on clan, religion, caste etc. Thus the village's neighbourhoods are recognized as Gujjar mohalla, Lambardaran da mohalla etc. Further, the lower castes are concentrated in the south-western end of the village whereas the Muslims, relatively new settlers in the village reside around the mosque towards the south of the village.
- The migrants to the village, labourers and daily wagers, are scattered throughout the fabric, as they primarily live as tenants. A major concentration of them occurs at the central area, the top of the mound just north of the Fort. The basic cause of this is the lack of municipal water supply, with a reduced pressure due to height, making the originally upper castes dwelling here shift to the fringes of

COMMUNITIES

the village or other parts of the city and lease their houses to migrant families.

A brief description of each community thus observed from the village and the city presents a clarified picture of their relation with the economic activities that are of interest here as well as the role played by them in the economy of the village and the city at this scale. It also helps in analysing their existing state and the potential they offer in the development of the fringe.

Native Village inhabitants:

- These are the families who had been living in the village before the existence of the city, primarily indulging in agricultural tasks.
- A majority of them own almost all of the land falling within the village limits, privately (abadi deh) or jointly (shamilat deh).
- Thus, with the land as an important resource at hand, and that too free from any restrictions, byelaws or controls, the owners exploit this potential by leasing it to other communities and enjoy the rental incomes as a replacement to their lost sources of livelihood - the agricultural lands - acquired by the government to establish the city.

Migrants inhabiting the village:

- They comprise of workers and labourers who settled in the village to participate in the growth of the developing city, as the village offered a better living environment and existing infrastructure and amenities compared to labour colonies or peripheral slums.
- Here, they seek employment in other commercial or industrial parts of the city but largely seek employment, either self or hired, in and around the village.
- However, the land costs for ownership or even leasing, is beyond the scope of migrants and hence, they turn to hawking/vending at the fringe thereby serving a larger customer base.

Residents of adjacent sectors:

- The people residing in the planned part of the city exploit the potential of the location of the fringe as well as the availability of cheap labour, space for commercial activities

ECONOMIC MODELS

- at relatively lower costs and a large customer base.
- Thus, they purchase the buildings or floors of built infrastructure at the outer face of the fringe on lease to run activities such as retail shops, stores, services, workshops, offices and low budget guesthouses and motels.
- On the other hand, it is again the people from the city and surrounding towns that avail the specialized services and goods offered by them.

These economic models based on communities are illustrated by the following diagrams.

Self-employment model

Native village residents

- Easy rental income
- Scope for economic mobility
- Fulfillment of consumer needs within proximity

Migrant

- Independent employment prospects
- Economic Sustenance

City dwellers

- Availability of cheap goods, products within proximity

- Ownership
- Flow of Products/Commodities/Services
- Flow of Money

Hired employment model

Native village residents

- Easy rental income
- Scope for economic mobility

Migrant

- Work employment prospects
- Economic Sustenance

City based small entrepreneurs

- Availability of cheap land on lease
- Flexibility of space and usage

- Most profitable alternative to run certain activities which might not be allowed in the city and are not economically feasible to run at the city's periphery

City dwellers

- Availability of cheap goods and services within proximity

INFERENCES

Native village inhabitants form an active part of the economy of the village and hence enjoy the freedom of socio-economic mobility and participation in the growth process of the city. A large number of them have already shifted to the city while retaining their village properties and leasing them. Although, the remaining inhabitants still hold the key to the prevalent socio-cultural continuity of the village and strong social ties, preserving the fabric, they cannot be denied in fulfilling their aspirations or their will to seek a better future. It becomes important, then, to benefit this community on sociological grounds so as to provoke a greater sense of belonging as well as through the intervention, make known, what belongs to them, to a wider public.

For the migrants, however, there is no facilitation from the government in terms of employment, or housing. They end taking up low end jobs or seek to be self-employed. They are considered as floating people temporarily settled in the village. It is this community, unemployed, with high rates of illiteracy clustered in congested spaces with ever deteriorating spatial quality and standards of living, which compels people to indulge in anti-social activities, thereby strengthening the relation of the urban village, as an entity, to its identity of an urban backyard of the city. Thus the primary beneficiaries for any intervention should be this population, also being a majority in numbers, and the upliftment of this community shall bridge the socio-economic gaps between the city and the urban villages.

The city residents on the other hand requires measures that allow them to penetrate the fringe more deeply. However, this does not mean that the interior of the village should be gentrified with residential settlement or high profile commercial activities being injected into the village, disrupting the existing socio-cultural fabric of the village. Such an objective can be achieved by exploiting the locational potential of the fringe and making available specialized goods & services at low costs and in proximity to dense residential settlements, as shown in the selection process for the proto-typical project site, improve the spatial quality and accessibility.

TOPOGRAPHY

The topography of the site is typical of traditional settlements which develop over a raised mound, to exploit the natural drainage of sewage as well as the discharge of rain water.

The gradient becomes flatter at the fringe area without any particular pattern. Thus, at the selected site, the gradient can be considered level for all practical purposes.

Contours depicting the gradient and elevation around the village Burail. The peak elevation at the centre is 331m while the average elevation for the village is 324m above sea level.

OPEN SPACES - VILLAGE INTERIOR

Typical open spaces existing in the village interior:

Streets (Non-thoroughfare/dead-end)

- Act as semi-public spaces, with the extension of residential activities into the public realm by the occupants residing in the abutting households
- Lack of thorough traffic discourages commercial activities from such spaces, and may only be located at the intersection with a major artery

Chowk

- A hub of public activity, physically evolved from a two or more streets intersecting in a common space
- Attracts community, institutional and commercial activities due to a high number of footfalls
- Daily necessities, small-scale retail, grocery & provision stores comprise of the built types while hawkers and vendors fill in for other activities

Chaupal

- A community owned and operated space primarily meant as a guesthouse and a platform for socio-cultural activities, ceremonies and functions
- It co-exists with places of worship, public and institutional buildings and allows for some small shops around

A chowk at the intersection of many streets, adjoining a school, a place of worship and a small clinic

A typical village 'Chaupal'

OPEN SPACES - FRINGE ZONES

Typical open spaces existing at the village fringe:

Chowk

- The intensity of commercial activities peaks out at major chowks, especially near the entry node of the village from where it mediates between various communities and consumer groups
- The domain of such activities ascends vertically creating multiple interfaces between consumers and retailers/service providers apart from the ground floor

Sabzi Mandi

- A nexus of migrants & native villagers provide such a spatial typology where, apart from generation of income, necessary requirements of the village as well as city's population residing in the adjoining sectors is met within proximity

Backyards

- Vacant plots or unused spaces near the fringe are mostly used as storage spaces, godowns, workshops supporting various activities abutting the circulatory roads, thereby spilling over the rear side than in the front

(Top) - A vegetable market run by migrants on an infill plot
(Middle) - Open ground for community functions, gatherings
(Below) - A waterworks pump being constructed in the middle of the village 'stadium' to meet the growing local demand

OPEN SPACES - BEYOND (PART OF SECTOR)

Open spaces beyond the limits of the village, are planned for recreation and leisure activities of the residents of the city. However, it succumbs under the pressure of the lack of such spaces within the village fabric. The spillover of activities from the village in addition to other non-recreational uses clutter the spaces. It is commonly encroached to cater the parking needs of private and commercial vehicles, loading and unloading from logistic support vehicles, etc.

INFERENCES

Therefore, from the analysis of open spaces in and around the village, the following inferences can be drawn:

- The open spaces within the old phirni limits still retain the old village character, primarily due to the continuity of their usage.
- However these spaces are limited and are gradually being converted into built areas to meet growing residential and commercial needs.
- The open spaces at the fringe have already been mostly encroached by commercial activities such as hawking/ vending by migrants, storage of goods for workshops and wholesale shops, building material stockists etc.
- There is a complete lack of green spaces for leisure and recreation which deprives the inhabitants from one the most important aspects determining the standard of living.
- Thus, it can be seen that only spaces which have a fixed role to play and are regulated by checking encroachment, survive in such an environment.

An open space part of Sector 45's green belt

- 17th century Burail Fort
- Chaupal
- Maidan, Janj Ghar, open green spaces
- Vacant lots

CONTAINED SPACES

Table showing possibility of activities in various container types and their extension, 'Spillage' over adjoining ground space

● Type available ○ Spill of Activity
 ● (blue) Spill of Storage ● (green) Spill of Display

Activities ▼	Village Fringe	City	Spill factor (max)
	Sq.m.	Sq.m.	
Retail	6 - 75	8 - 300	30%
Retail-cum-Services	12 - 50	8 - 540	70%
Workshop-cum-Service	15 - 50	8 min.	25%
Workshops	10 - 30	16 min.	40%
Hawkers/Vendors	4 - 10		N.A.
Offices	12 - 60	16 min.	0%

Table showing typical area requirements based upon proto-types existing in the village fringe area, the city & the associated spillage

Area (Location)	
Types ▼	Sq.m.
Booths	8, 9.6, 13.2, 17(Along V3's)
Shops (Inner markets)	82.5(Sec 22D), 105(Sec 22C), 92.8(Sec 22D), 89.9(Sec 35D)
Showrooms	257(Sec 8, Madhya Marg), 195(Sec 22, Dakshin Marg)

Table showing typical areas as per a few types available in the city

The following photographs provide a visual reference to the various activities and their organization in contained spaces throughout the fringes of the village.

OFFICES

RETAIL

SERVICES

MOTELS/GUESTHOUSES

WORKSHOPS

Circulation

PATTERN

Here, the circulation pattern, its growth and evolution, the spaces it utilizes and the cognitive qualities that make them highly legible over the planned streets in the city are analysed.

- The pattern of streets within the old phirni evolved directly from the initial parcels of land owned by different settlers in the village around the central mound and the fort, through subsequent subdivisions amongst their offsprings, families or workers.
- Thus, an original tract of land would eventually have streets running all around them, and as the subdivision required plots being cast away from the periphery, inward branching of tertiary streets started developing.
- However, at the fringe, there is no fixed pattern formed by the street network. Although, ideally the radial streets should extend upto the new phirni across the extended abadi area. Here the pattern is haphazard with abrupt dead ends and is ineffectively connected with the internal, loop of the old phirni.

The pattern evolved within the phirni limits attains certain objective qualities for cognition. These are experienced kinaesthetically with a high degree of legibility, even though the pattern maybe organic. These cognitive qualities are lent by the following factors:

COGNITIVE QUALITIES

- Gradation: While traversing through them, there is a gradation of density, intensity of activity as well as public life as one moves away from nodes towards the interiors. This can also be experienced along the hierarchy of streets, where the main bazaar streets are the most active, with commercial activities abutting and also the widest. Whereas branching secondary and tertiary streets are mostly residential, semi-public, especially where they terminate in a dead end and less in widths.
- Articulation: Due to the compactness of the village, most public buildings, structures, forming landmarks lie along the major streets, which also happen to be of the longest length. These landmarks, intersections and nodes help in articulation of the long stretches of streets by breaking the monotony, and hence helping in the legibility as the fragments are perceived in a same fixed sequence.

The initial subdivision of land conjectured through the continuity of major radial streets as well as the existing 'mohallas' provides an insight into the subsequent branching of tertiary streets and hence the evolution of pattern

Street Profile - Village interior

Street Profile - Main Bazaar

Circulatory road (Phirni) at Fringe

The resulting form of the circulation spaces is a result of the rapid urbanization and economic growth of the village, without any regulating mechanisms in place to control it. High demands for residences and commercial space within the village leads to exploitation of the conditions by landowners who tend to expand the leasable space by all means, often covering the entire span of the narrow alleys by cantilevering upper floor levels.

This results in the handshake conditions at the upper levels and the circulation space at the ground level is embedded in a solid mass of private, enclosed spaces around it, making it difficult for habitable spaces at the lower levels to receive any direct light or proper ventilation.

However, such streets have continued to develop since long and also have certain positives, which include:

- During imperial times, such a street network helped in the defense of towns, making them hard to penetrate by huge armies during attacks.
- The volume is partially insulated towards climatic extremes and enables its usage and the continuity of activities during a greater range of weather conditions.

The following matrices present a quantitative analysis of the circulation spaces and paths, their relation to the physical environment which contains them as well as the intangible aspects of the activities that take place along them.

Thus, the street types existing in and around the villages can be categorized as follows, based upon the accessibility at the edge and the nature of traffic which occurs along them.

Further, the type of activities and the nature of traffic depends upon the hierarchy in a typical street plan. These include the terminal streets, the thoroughfares, chowks (nodes), abutting spaces falling in the villages' fringe zone; and the activities supported by

Circulation spaces matrix - showing a quantitative analysis

Relation between Nature of Activity & Open spatial types - Relative analysis

Architectural Character

PATTERN - ORGANIZATION

The architectural character of the context is analysed in terms of its formal outlook as well as the organization of spaces. The market forces and the narrow interface with a high potential make the owners exploit the condition and with a tendency to economize space, the residual spaces such as the streets or open public spaces are encroached upon, especially at the upper levels. Thus the spatial character of the zone is dominated by the embedded streets.

Apart from the physical environment, the activities existing at the fringe also have an important role to play in defining the experience for the perception of the space. The spillage of activities, especially those including auto-repair, services, junk and scrap dealers, stockists of building material, workshops relating to building materials, etc. often acts as a repulsive facade over the fringe of the village, thereby limiting the penetrability.

VISUAL CHARACTER

There is no formal character of the buildings at the fringe, the perceived visual appearances of the physical environment comprises of either market driven, ad-hoc constructions or limitations of architectural forms and executed with individualist expressionism, often by the owners or the contractors themselves. Thus, the resultant picture can be best described as a 'bricolage' of buildings built during different times and in different styles, lacking a single coherent appeal.

On the other hand, the city which offered a coherent, modernist character expressed in brick and concrete in most of the constructions of the first phase, with its expansion into the second and third phase, adopts styles prevalent not only in other parts India but across the whole world.

Thus, relating visually to the context is neither possible, nor viable for projects designed in the contemporary era, primarily due to the multiplicity of existing styles as well as the vagueness of the limits of the concept of context. Such a gap is fulfilled by the associating the architecture to be developed with its context 'typologically', as discussed in Chapter 3.

The 'embedded streets' typology, perceived as a residue of the abutting built forms, lends the village as existing today, a cohesive & imageable spatial character

VISUAL REFERENCE

A panorama of the 'Old PNB' Chowk, adjacent to the entry node of the village

Retail + Banquet facilities at ZONE 1

17th Century Fort bastions at the heart of the village

Mixed-Use complex at ZONE 3

SCO's at ZONE 2

Adjoining School building

Typical commercial complex for Phase II sectors - Regimentation

Adjacent temple in sector 46

Booths in sector 34

Functional Aspects

SPILLAGE

Another important aspect that reserves the potential to provide inferences for an intervention including relating to commercial and economic activities, is the organization and operational patterns of those existing within and around the village. A major factor that differentiates the commercial strips of the city and the bazaars and the fringe markets of the village is the Spillage, or spill over of activities from contained spaces into open spaces.

The degree or nature of the 'spilled' activity is directly affect the experiential aspects of the spaces, visually and physically. The apparent intensity of activity, or 'street life' is, partially, a result of such spillage. However, not all spill-overs are conducive in generating a healthy, spatial environment and may adversely affect it, such as - repair shops, workshops, junk dealers, etc. which form a major part of the 'fringe' belt of the village and are clustered together, thus creating alternate fragments

Container Types: City based typology

'Spillage' - extension of activities from contained spaces into open spaces - inversely proportional to container volume.

Small volume
 >Density in no's
 >Spillage
 >Intensity of Activity
 >Vibrancy in Street life

Operational Structures: 1. City types

2. Village periphery

- Thorough traffic circulation
- Customers/Consumer traffic circulation
- Logistics, services, freight
- Spillover of activity

Comparing the Operational Structures of typical commercial establishments

OPERATIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Design Objectives

ACCESSIBILITY & PERMEABILITY

Need to provide vehicular accessibility across the zone in addition to improved spatial quality. Presently, the zone has a haphazard character. The network of streets is also hazardous & complex.

'Fringe' as a linear, barrier-like interface

'Fringe' as a permeable zone - a catalyst for interaction between various communities

OPEN PUBLIC SPACES

Within the village, the few left-over open spaces are encroached upon for commercial activities, hawking/vending or as backyards/storage areas for workshops and service activities. Thus, one of the prime objectives is to generate and redevelop open spaces within the village. Prevention from encroachment by improving the spaces quality of the commercial belt.

Beyond the village limits, the open spaces for the city are used as parking lots for the residential population of the village, the customers to various activities at the fringe as well as by commercial vehicles.

Thus, there is a need to include public open spaces along the fringe zone to support the commercial viability as well as facilitate social interactions between different user communities.

INCLUSION OF MIGRANTS/STREET VENDORS

Need to provide spaces and a framework for the facilitation of migrants & daily wagers. These migrants constitute more than 60% of Burail's population and provide cheap goods and services to residents of the village and the city in return of economic sustenance and mobility. As majority of the land is owned by the native village dwellers, the revenue from leases shall benefit them and hence extend to all the communities through this holistic model.

City: Policy constraints

Village: Space constraints
+ Lack of customers due to limited accessibility

'Fringe' as the preferred location for facilitating migrants/daily wagers seeking to be self-employed through hawking/vending etc.

TRAFFIC ORGANIZATION

Congestion is caused at due to conflict and intersections between various traffic types and simultaneous use of the limited circulation space at the interface for various traffic related activities, such as:

- Thorough traffic
- Access to buildings
- Parking
- Services/Repair

Thus, need to segregate and organize various traffic types and activities along the fringe fabric

Chapter 3

Type & Typology

Typological Working On Type

INTRODUCTION

Categorization of built form in terms of their initial purpose is now being increasingly deemed regressive, as evidenced by the examples above. The permanent nature of structures conflicts with the changing need of man. The function of an average building type in an urban area now changes so often that an adaptable, pliable structure is inevitable. Buildings now need to be independent of their initial function.

Classifying buildings according to genres flexible enough to allow them to transgress their functional and formal limitations is the need of these dynamic times. A step closer towards achieving this flexible nature is found in typology – the science of type.

QUATREMERÉ'S TYPE

An element, an object, an abstraction; type is defined as anything that embodies the idea according to Quatremere de Quincy, the first to advocate a typological classification. The type can be abstract and conceptual rather than concrete or literal. It is, in nutshell, an ideal that an architect should strive for, that can be easily replicated, yet adapt according to the site, need and any other constraint. With changing times, new types emerge.

Typological design models are capable of and require, rather than facilitate, transformation and hybridization in order to fulfil the ambitions and requirements of an architectural project in the urban context. New types emerge in response to requirements of a changing society.

VALIDITY

The current times have brought with them modernist theorists, championing the cause of ripping a structure of all its baggage – its past and social character – to make it as practical and functional as possible. That, however, also leaves an urban area devoid of its historical background. Typology helps by acting as an index of elemental parts of the plan - not mere graphic representation of urban plan but embody organisational performance, history, meaning since it is born out of the changing needs of the inhabitants themselves. Thus, a typological model equates architecture's capacity for progressive development with its sociality. Architecture as a profession is today facing problems unparalleled before. The rapid urbanisation has led to

JNL, Durand - Facade combinations

architects merely responding to the changes and challenges. In relation to a city, these problems increase manifolds leading to a separation of architecture and urban planning. This leaves each of them unable to deal with the fast-changing context. Furthermore, a market economy, driven by the need to innovate just for the sake of it adds to the problems at hand.

The inability to describe, conceptualize and express any new ideas in relation to the city is a handicap that can have repercussions in the form of not only increasingly haphazard, chaotic cities, but also ripped of their soul. Typological models thus provide a new solution – both diagnostic and projective in nature.

In order to acquaint oneself to current global practices, the following studies have been added. They include an internet study and two on site analysis of types in the local context.

Xi'an Horticultural Masterplan

The following study showcases how a historical, formal 'type' transcends function and evolves with time. The interpretation of a historic, peripheral wall as a horticulture exposition hub is a paradigm of typological working.

BACKGROUND

The historic city of Xi'an, China is encircled by a wall measuring 25.7 km for protection. Although now rendered useless, it is historically significant and cannot be altogether done away with. However, since it blocks access to the city's periphery, it needs to be made traversable and more interactive in a way that does not curb expansion.

SERIE ARCHITECTS

The Serie Architects' design team, as an entry for proposed horticulture hub here, came up with a solution that converts the closed city wall into an open, inviting and interactive one. The competition brief called for the design of a greenhouse and associated facilities. The proposal reinterprets the horticulture master plan, not as a landscape design but, as a large 'architectural artifact' that continues the tradition of city-making in Xi'an throughout the ages simply by translating the boundary wall into a strong feature of the design.

COMPETITION PROPOSAL

The closed city wall is reconceived as a linear structure marking the centre of the site. This 1 km long linear stretch consists of five greenhouses, each having a different climatic zone. The Five Climates Crossing not only delineates the centre but also acts as a connector between the entrance square in the north and the viewing tower in the south. The peripheral wall is thus revived as a typological device to both mark the centre as well as connect it to the entrance.

The northern tip of the Five Climates Crossing forms the entrance square measuring 210m by 210m, planned to serve both as an exhibition area as well as an open performing area. Radiating pavement lines focus the circulation and attention to the entrance steps and centre of the square. Within the crossing, visitors can move sequentially from one greenhouse to another while maintaining a visual connect to the outside. The Chang'an Park located at the centre of the wall houses a concert hall, exhibition halls, restaurants, lounges, etc. the use of parabolic vaults here that creates volumetric interest.

The typological transformation diagram

INFERENCES

'Type transcends function'

The typological transformation of a city wall into greenhouses and a bridge allows the use of a single architectural feature to create a new centrality on the periphery of the city, reconsolidating its peripheral fragments and bridging the existing city. The traditional too, remains preserved even as it makes way for the changing needs.

Thus it can be seen how with the use of a formal type, with a precise function, is transformed into a new architecture serving a different purpose but relating typologically to the historicity of the context.

'Type' in local context

INTRODUCTION

Cities are a veritable melting pot of cultures, people, and traditions. People relocate to cities due to the apparent economic gains, making it their own. Thus, there are reciprocal implications between societies and the character of cities. This further changes with the times and needs. Since the city is constantly evolving and growing, its history is preserved through its architecture – specifically buildings like town halls, libraries etc. in the western context whereas imperial palaces and places of worship, conforming to Indian subcontinent. They record layers of changes and the reasons leading to it. These dominant types of buildings communicate the idea of city in response to historical, socio-cultural conditions.

The advent of modernist planning principles too, preaches conceptualization and construction of such building types that are devoid of anything but the bare most functions and still fulfill its need functionally.

"...the typical did not provide just a model for the production of the singular artifact – be it a built component, a piece of furniture, dwelling unit or the urban block. It provided a framework for conceptualizing architecture as part of a social & ideological agenda."

OBJECTIVES

To understand the notion of 'types' in the local context, the following two case studies help in tracing the factors that guide their inception, transformation and relation or dependency with form and function, etc. The primary objective here is to seek what the modernist typical modules have to offer for a typological association. It primarily focuses on considering the two containers, amongst others, developed by Le Corbusier and his team for the commercial zones of the city, popularised as the 'Shop-cum-Offices' (SCO's) and the 'Booths'.

Case Study - Booth Markets

The following study traces the linkages between the typical modules created by Le Corbusier and his associates and the growth and evolution of informal markets along with the creation of new architectural types – the booth markets.

HISTORICAL CONTEXT

The program based zoning within the different sectors, although intended to cater to a broad range of the existing social hierarchy, could not foresee the singularities arising from a phase wise development of sectors, instead of a one-time construction of the entire built fabric, that would have been neither practical nor feasible. Shop-cum-Flats and Shop-cum-Offices, the containers provided for commercial activities in the new city, based on modernist principles, could adapt to any kind of activities and usage. However, the needs of the lower strata of the society could not be met through them. The low-end services did not require such large containers either, especially with the city in its embryonic stage. Sub-division of this space was also discouraged by stringent policies and controls. Acquiring an S.C.O would, therefore, on one hand result in the redundancy of space and on the other hand, cost a person much more than he could afford, without a guarantee of reasonable returns. Although the shopping centres also included strips of booths, their location was based upon the conceived masterplan, and did not respond to the emerging hubs in the developing city.

Thus, neither was the entire spectrum of the society catered to, nor did the containers themselves suffice for the vast range of activities to be carried out.

THE EVOLUTION

At this time in its development, the new city, as a place full of opportunities, was attracting people from other small towns wanting to make a living and settle here. Besides, people displaced by the partition saw the chance to rehabilitate and start over in the new city. State government employees who worked and settled here also formed a major part of the growing population. Realizing the potential for sale of inexpensive goods and services, and also due to their own economic situation, hawking and vending became the migrants' medium of earning a livelihood. Since small markets were largely absent from the scheme of the city, these hawker groups gained popularity. This was the birth of a type which

evolved parallel to the city's 'planned' containers, and hence this combination of the people not catered to and activities not conceived, organizing themselves into informal markets sought to bridge the missing gaps.

ORGANIZATION & OPERATION

Though illegal and informal, these pattri/rehrimarkets, were organized in their own meticulous way. The vendor phenomenon of wanting to stay among healthy competition led to the aggregation of those selling similar goods. This function-based arrangement was also useful to the owners for helping gain popularity as particular areas started specializing in the goods or services they provided. While rehriwallas with similar goods banded together, they also excluded anyone from anywhere near their area, wanting to sell something completely different. It was only natural. Why would a group of vendors selling eatables want repair shops on their precincts? Or clothes-sellers have metal scrap dealers nearby them?

The principles of aggregation and exclusion lead to a very systematic organization, subject to not only function but also the social and economic needs of the times. These bands of rehri were so efficient, in fact, that upon allocation of land to them, they convened themselves into areas of fixed dimensions of 8'x8', and adhered to them. This very organization of spaces into fixed areas was the precursor to the architectural type that can now be called booth markets.

These hawker groups thus, organized themselves according to their own needs as well as the needs of the people and thus incorporated the social fabric of India in defining the character of the informal markets, something that the formally constructed modern shopping strips were lacking.

INFORMAL TO FORMAL

With the advent of time, the next step in this trajectory was the demand for permanent structures from which they could sell their wares. The growing success as well as popularity of the informal vendor markets made it possible to generate enough clout to make the government give in to these demands. The Architectural Dept. of Chandigarh Administration looked upon the existing, working examples available around them to derive inferences for the formalization of a new 'architectural

type' in the city. Hence, whereas the smaller booth modules provided for the design of a repetitive unit, the self-organized layouts and operational patterns helped in the organization of these units into a market complex.

It was thus, a perfect marriage of the ad-hoc self-organization of the people responding to socio-economic needs of the time with the typical modernist containers, catering to the requirements with an optimum utilization of space. It is due entirely to this perfect amalgamation that booth markets now thrive throughout the city.

PATEL MARKET, SECTOR 15

Among these successful markets are Patel market, sector 15, Shastri market, sector 22 and the more recent book shops in sector 15.

Vendors in Patel market, sector 15, have arranged themselves around small courtyards, each unit distinct in its function and character, though similar spatially. It results in a market that has open spaces after each street, forming a square that is flooded with natural light. Here, too, the principle of aggregation has been applied, resulting in each square dedicated to similar goods or services. Dhabas, for example are grouped around the end of the market, while clothes stores enjoy prime location and are clustered around the various entries.

The sector 15 book shops provide a completely different study. These vendors were located on the roadside, their wares i.e. the books themselves, stacked high, served as boundaries. Thus, these vendors too had arranged themselves into fixed dimensions. Their demand for permanent structures was met with a longitudinal shed, with sloping roofs. Through the middle of the structure lies a passage with shops on either side. Here too aggregation can be observed in the form of those selling textbooks being separate from the ones selling novels.

This precedent of spatial organization can also be observed in local 'apni mandis'. Hawkers and vendors arrange themselves into fixed areas, without any physical barriers.

CONCLUSION

The preceding study of the evolution of a new architectural type – the booth markets was inspired by the parallel existing typical modules of the booths, their self-organization and operational patterns of the migrant population and early settlers in the new city. It makes the reading of these types a critique of the socio-economic conditions through which they evolved.

Case Study - SCO typology INTRODUCTION

Shop-cum-Office, (S.C.O) a term nobody in a tiny village that preceded Chandigarh 60 years ago would have thought of that term. If not for the advent of the modernists, the S.C.O, as we know it today wouldn't have existed in our consciousness. The fact that it is so prevalent throughout the region now is worthy of scrutiny.

The following study traces the introduction of a new a typical module into the socio-economic framework of a developing city and how its adaptation and transformation responds to the context of the emerging needs and resulting conditions that gave birth to a new architectural type. The dependency of the evolution of a type on form and function has also been analyzed with respect to its replication outside the city. Succeeding the catastrophe of the violent partition of India, Chandigarh was a gift to the province of Punjab by the Central Government. The intent was to help not only forget the past but to also showcase the might of the new nation. The foreign architects and town planners summoned for the purpose thus created a city that, instead of being an outcome of the natural growth of the existing villages into towns and then a city, was an imported implant.

THE CITY & ITS CONTAINERS

Along with the planning and designing of the city, the containers for various commercial and economic activities to cater to the conceived needs of a city of this kind were designed with a modernist ideology. Although practical, the SCO types bypassed any relation or inheritance from the existing types available in the region, primarily because the regional containers did not have to cater such programs. The SCO's provided a framework with flexibility of program and organization.

DEPARTURE FROM CONVENTIONAL TRAJECTORY

The existing villages, on the other hand, being agrarian settlements, could not have grown beyond a certain size, owing to administrative restrictions as well as a lack of stimuli, factors which catapult growth and give rise to cities. Had this been the case, these very villages would have followed completely different trajectories of growth, physical and social – imbibing the best of what was locally available or depending upon the zone of influence and era of development, apart from the nature of settlement. But here, the implementation of the foreign town planning changed its course of development drastically, or rather initiated a growth and development process.

The needs and conditions of growth emerge from within a settlement – rising trade, its economic mobility and the ability of a town/city to retain the wealth produced. In this case, the establishment of a new city, adjacent and around the villages, created unique urban conditions.

FORCED INCLUSION CREATING UNIQUE CONDITIONS

Once the new city accumulated enough population, growing beyond a particular size, its interaction with the existing villages created peculiar challenges as well as potentials. People, the native village population and the residents of the city, now wanted to participate in the growth process of the city, aspiring success and economic mobility synonymous with it. Thus, they looked upon the now successful commercial vessels used, the S.C.O to accomplish their aspirations.

Another aspect governing the change was the land acquisition policy adopted by the government, which eroded the primary source of livelihood of the villagers, who were forced to seek alternate sources of income for sustenance. Therefore, a

rising demand for commercial activities especially goods and services at cheaper costs along with much lower land prices, sparked off the construction of commercial spaces all around the existing villages, the interface of the 'planned' and the 'unplanned'. The high locational potential of this zone was consequently realized.

ADOPTED TYPES

The interface, or the fringe zone of the villages, thus witnessed rapid urbanization which was a result of the freedom which private owners, entrepreneurs enjoyed and the ability to freely provide for the demands. However, the containers that were adopted for the supply of commercial spaces did not bear resemblance to the existing types in the village, nor were they transformations of those types, suiting the needs and requirements of this unique conditions. They picked up the dominant S.C.O. modules from the city, 'regimented' along the commercial strips, for their flexibility.

Another reason the S.C.O type was favored by the natives and the migrants alike, was a result of the ideological agenda which formed the basis of the conception of the city, owing to the nations then Prime Minister, Pt. Jawahar Lal Nehru. Thus, the new, modern and foreign was aspired over the traditional. Such a phenomena can be traced to the colonial times, when a strict political and sociological agenda was followed by the colonizers to demean the natives of everything that belonged to them.

The S.C.O was thus, in time, universally accepted, reinforced by various factors.

TRANSFORMATIONS

Burial, an island of a village settlement surrounded by Chandigarh on all sides, too now makes optimum use of the module provided by the planners of the city. Not only has it been replicated in the neighborhood satellite towns of Panchkula and Mohali, but peripheral agglomerations and sprawls like Kharar and Zirakpur too show the type, albeit carrying along transformations due to various constraints. In Burial, these transformations include a narrowed width but increase in the number of floors. The front corridor and balconies are absent to optimize space. The aesthetics have also been played with, expressing the desires of the people to

CONCLUSION

have their buildings stand out amongst others, contrary to the monotonous, regimentation of S.C.O's in the city.

On the other hand, the peripheral settlements conform more genuinely to the organization and the structural arrangement of spaces, but depart further in terms of the aesthetics. The transformations thus, are only superficial. The structural organization of spaces remains the same – which is the primary essence of the formal aspect of a type. The aesthetic variations merely assist the visual experience.

The S.C.O. type not only adapted to the various functions and unique conditions it was subjected to, but also fulfilled the indigenous needs of the native village people with time. It transformed and evolved to better suit the immediate requirements, thus remaining true to its flexible nature. Thus it can be read that the formal aspects of an architectural type, adhered to in their true essence, the flexibility offered in terms of function enable a typical modernist framework to displace the historically rich, formal types in a region. Although this ignores the historicity of what existed prior to the advent of the modernists, the socio-political agenda, ideology and the historical aspects of which marked the establishment of the city are contained within this type.

Diagram

The 'Street' typology

"...new types emerge in response of a changing society and urban conditions, whereby the typological diagrams are adapted to the constraints of specific sites. This notion of type as a model, graphically reducible to diagrams, introduced precepts that are fundamental to working typologically" - Chris Lee, Introduction to AD Jan-Feb '11

SELECTION

The design for the commercial complex - an intervention aimed at restructuring the fringe thus required a 'type'. The characteristics or potentials for the type require it to have a legible form, objective qualities for imageability and a strong presence. On the other hand, its potential in retaining, conveying critical information about the society of which it is a tangible part, is as important as its relevance when adopted, transformed and planted into a new context for, perhaps a different function.

The streets of the village offer such qualities and potentials. The following are some of the benefits in adopting the street type as an initiating diagram for the socio-physical restructuring of the fringe of the village.

BENEFITS

- The embedded form of the streets is an outcome of the socio-economic processes, tracing the evolution of the society and the physical containers it dwells in.
- The degree of embedment of the street passage coincides with the maturity or the urbanization of the traditionally grown settlements.
- Such street typologies are omnipresent and synonymous with the urban village phenomena, thus a large section of the society easily associates themselves with them.
- The proposed program and function of the commercial complex, as well as its role as a social catalyst, makes the street typology an appropriate choice in ordering and organizing the vast range of activities that shall be supported, with the circulation pattern a common denominator to all.
- Therefore, the adoption of the street typology puts forth the historicity of the urbanized village, and its implantation at the interface between the village and the city helps the city dwellers to experience the traditional typology associated with a precise socio-economic function and a wider

objective of 'symbiotic cohabitation'.

MORPHING & TRANSGRESSING

The adoption process also inculcates the modernist planning principles. Here it is evident how the circulation, access formed the primary ordering and organizing tool for planning and design at all scales of architecture and urbanism. Le Corbusiers master plan for the design of the city divides it into various districts connected with an underlying grid at the city scale. On the neighbourhood scale, his sketch for the neighbourhood block, the sector unit, was organized along a hierarchical arrangement of streets.

Thus the adoption of the 'street' typology for this design project, not only morphs the two contrasting systems of planning with different evolutionary trajectories but at the same time transgresses the architectural characteristics in an attempt to create a new architectural type at the fringe responding to the contextual factors and the socio-economic needs of the striated society in consideration.

'FRINGE' PROTO-TYPE

The development of the diagram from the initiating elements, the 'street typologies', also incorporates the contextual constraints, challenges and potentials arising from the unique urban conditions as highlighted in Chapter 2. Therefore the diagram becomes a graphical model which can be explored in a different contexts, generating different resultant designs each time owing to different factors, such as the people, spatial environment, existing functions and programmatic requirements, etc. Thus, a proto-typical diagram for the fringe type of architecture primarily comprises of streets with cognitive qualities of those in the village and the ordering and organizing principles, enforced by the circulation paths, devised by centralized planning, to enable participatory activities and a holistic growth.

The following steps explain the development and transformation of the types into a diagram that shall guide the design for the intervention.

Diagram Development

PARALLEL ARRAY OF CIRCULATION PATHS

- Accessibility throughout the entire allowable volume
- Traffic distribution and segregation
- Reduction in congestion

DEFORMATION OF PATHS EXPOSED TO CONTEXTUAL NODES (ATTRACTOR POINTS)

- Direct connection between nodes - thus making the volume easily accessible for the majority of the thorough pedestrian traffic
- Vertical accessibility to be located near nodes
- Thus minimizing circulation and dependency on signage and wayfinding along with increased commercial viability along thoroughfares

TRANSLATION OF PATHS INTO CIRCULATION - HORIZONTAL & VERTICAL

- The translation of the diagram primarily as the circulation pattern - horizontal and vertical as an organizing tool for various spaces, activities and programs.
- The cognitive qualities of the streets in the village are inherited to promote the historical associativity with the village's physical environment

PROGRAMMATIC DELINEATION WITHIN BALANCE VOLUME (CONTAINED SPACES)

- Arrangement in accordance with the requirements of various activities and mutual co-existence

- Retail stores, shops, services
- Offices
- Hospitality - bed & breakfast motels

